

Oronymic Dimension and Branch of Oronymics
(on the basis of materials of Samarkand region)

Linguistics

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Abstract

Oronym, oronymic terms are analysed on the basis of Samarkand region materials, oronymic dimension of the Uzbek language, oronymic objects are defined, sphere of oronymics and its issues to study, several tasks of Uzbek oronymics are given in this article. Important information about relations of oronyms with other types of toponymics: oykonym, hydronym, urbonym, drymonym, phitonym, zoonym; connection with folklore, history, geography. As a result of scientific researches in the sphere of Uzbek toponymy some scientists worked on oronymy. Besides oronymics as a department of toponymics has its object and subject to study. The ancientness, stability, including different historical-geographical information; demand to study such subjects as history, geography, archeology, country study and linguistics; implementation of experiments of world onomastics into Uzbek oronymics; creating etymological, practical transcriptional-comparative dictionaries are the most actual tasks of Uzbek toponymics.

The proper names of orographic objects in the Uzbek language toponymy compose particular semantic group. Oronyms have defined as following in scientific sources of toponymy. S.Karimov and S.Buriev considered that oronyms are “names of mountains” and such words as peak, hill, upland, pass, canyon, precipice can be included into this group [3, p. 45]

T. Ernazarov explains the branch terms as following: “Oronym-the name of uplands, highlands, mountains, hills. Oronymy is the complex of names of highlands, uplands, mountains and hills. Oronymics is the branch which study the names of highlands, uplands, mountains and hills” [6, p. 78]. The scientist supposes to include the names of mountains, hills and cliffs [6, p. 80].

S. Koraev wrote: “Oronym (oros-mountain, onoma-name) is the name of mountains, hills, uplands, hollows and other orographic names” [13, p. 193]. He also supposed that “Oronyms include not only the names of mountain stones, but also the names of valleys, hills, precipices, hollows, uplands and sandy places ”[15, p. 66].

Z. Dusimov and M.Tillaeva consider the term of oronymy as “types and patterns of relief (upland and depth of the Earth)”[2, p. 82].

The term of oronymy is explained more perfectly in terminological dictionary of E.Begmatov, N.Ulukov: “Oronym (greek. orog-mountain+onoma-proper name)” is the proper name of any high objects on the earth’s relief (mountain, hill, highland, peak, pass and others) [1, p. 63]. To say in short, oronyms are special proper names of orographic objects [5, p. 105].

Only the names of mountains and peaks are included into oronyms in some literatures on Russian toponymics [4, p. 24].

Though the term oronymy lexically means “the name of mountain”, it has a wide range of meanings. The proper names of mountains, mountain ranges, uplands, passes, highlands, cliffs, peaks, mounds and other orographic objects which mean other physical-geographic places are included into oronyms.

The toponymy of Samarkand region of the Republic of Uzbekistan is also characterized with richness of oronyms. Samarkand region is located in western part of Pamir-Alay mountains, in the middle of Zerafshan river. The relief mainly stretched over width and includes mountain ranges of Turkistan in the north (Nurota mountain, height 2169 m, Oktog, 2003m) and Zerafshan valley surrounded with Zerafshan mountain ranges in the south. The valley is descended from east (750-800m) to west (350m). There are plains on the slope to north and south, and hills near to mountain [11,463]. Mountain ranges of Samarkand region are divided into several low hills. Such oronyms as Ayribel, Beshbarmak, Gubdintov, Jalkir, Mirhaydar, Murtog, Choltosh, Turatov, Chambar, Chigatoytov, Kizbibi mean those hills.

As the result of dialectological investigations, we collected the following names of orographic objects: names of mountains – 219, names of mountain ranges – 19, names of peaks – 54, names of cliffs – 6, names of passes – 31, names of caves – 43, names of stones – 72, names of canyons – 17, names of ditches – 9, names of ledges – 16, names of stages – 4, names of hills – 819, names of uplands – 56, names of highlands – 71. As it is clear from the facts, the notion of oronyms has a wide range from the onomastic point of view. The names of these objects compose special semantic group, oronyms in onomastic layer of the Uzbek language, i.e. oronymy. Special proper names of these objects can be included into group of oronyms of the Uzbek language on the basis of Samarkand region materials:

1. **Names of mountains:** *Bugchakurgontog* (Urgut district Boykishlok village), *Gardantog* (Urgut district Kamongaron village), *Ettikiztogi* (Urgut district Kuzichi village), *Zinaktog* (Urgut district Yangikishlok village), *Murtog* (Payarik district), *Oynakortogi* (Urgut district Boykishlok village), *Oytulditog* (Urgut district Ayrikoya village), *Suvombortogi* (Urgut district Urtakishlok village), *Teshiktog* (Ishtikhan district).

2. **Names of mountain ranges:** (large relief forms with straight downhills in both sides) *Turkistan mountain ranges*, *Zerafshan mountain ranges* [12, p. 573].

3. **Names of passes:** (the highest point of mountain and hills) orographic terms *agba*, *akba*, *obga*, *avga*, *kutal*, *oshuv* is considered as paradigm with *bel* in the Uzbek language: *Ayribel* (Nurobot district), *Kumbelsoy* (Urgut district Konsoy village), *Tukchabel* (Kushrabot district), *Urtabel* (Nurobot district).

4. **Names of peaks:** (the highest place of mountain) *Bobomurodchukki* (Urgut district Ayrikoya village), *Zardolichukki* (Kushrabot district Kuvkalla village), *Zinnonchukki* (Urgut district Konsoy village), *Islomchukki* (Urgut district Korabulok village), *Okchukki* (Urgut district Oktosh village), *Sattorchukki* (Urgut district Kizilturik village), *Toshtemirchukki* (Urgut district Ayrikoya village), *Chodirchukki* (Ishtikhan district Boytupi village), *Eshkulchukki* (Urgut district Boykishlok village).

5. **Names of cliffs:** the indicator cliff (koya) is used in following meanings:
 – cliff, hill which is made by hard matters (mainly, when the mountain stones moulder);
 – high straight cliff [10, p. 353]. And also is meaningful with koya and koyatosh. For instance, *Ayrikoya* (Urgut district Ayrikoya village), *Belboglikoya* (urgut district Ayrikoya village), *Kizilkoya* (Urgut district Beshbulok village).

6. **Names of whirlpools:** *Kizilkamar* (Kattakurgan district), *Teshikkamar* (Urgut district in the south of Khujavaholik).

7. **Names of canyons:** canyon (dara) is etymologically Persian word, is means the road in the mountain, ravine. It is used as long, narrow road in the mountain, ravine in the Uzbek language [7, p. 556]. Synonym of this word may be precipice (zov) and means the ravine between mountains [8, p. 157]. *Dakhanalidara* (Urgut district, Kamongaron village), *Kaptardayra* (Urgut district Tersak village), *Tangidara* (Ishtikhan district Sortokchi village), *Tollikdara* (Urgut district Kizilbosh village), *Chapdara* (Urgut district Abdukishlok village), *Zov* (Urgut district Vagashti village), *Zovdor* (near Urgut town), *Kizilzov* (Urgut district Tegirmonboshi village).

8. **Names of ledges:** *Kumgaza* (Nurabad district in western part of Koratepa range), *Maymungaza* (Urgut district Beshbulok village), *Tikgaza* (Kushrabot district).

9. **Names of stages:** *Supatoshtog* (Urgut district Boykishlok village), *Paygambarsupa* (Urgut district Beshkal village), *Amirsupa* (Kattakutgon district Yangikurgoncha village).

10. **Names of ditches:** (dangerous straight ravine) *Laylayuchma* (Urgut district Lakkon village).

11. **Names of caves:** the word cave (gor) etimologically Arabian word and means ravine, deepness [9, p. 289]. It is used as under the hill, mountain in the Uzbek language [10, p. 454]. For instance, *Devkhonagori* (Urgut district Boykishlok village), *Zumradgor* (Urgut district Ayrikoya village), *Kismokgor* (Kushrabot district Kuvkalla village), *Kuyligor* (Ishtikhan district Boytupi village), *Nurchagor* (Kattakugon district Arabkhona village), *Terakgor* (Urgut district Tersak village), *Turpogor* (Urgut district Boykishlok village), *Chiltongor* (Urgut district Bakhir village), *Sharragor* (Urgut district Konsoy village).

12. **Names of stones:** *Ajdartosh* (Kushrabot district Kizilbel village), *Buzaktosh*, *Gildiraktosh*, *Yomontosh*, *Kayroktosh* (Urgut district Ayrikoya village), *Darvozatosh* (Urgut district Beshbulok village), *Kelinchaktosh* (Urgut district Koratepa village), *Odamtosh* (Ishtikhan district Dustlik village), *Oytosh* (Urgut district Chep village).

13. **Names of hills:** *Kuchtepa* (Kattakugon district Tuynak village), *Semiztepa* (Pakhtachi district Karnob village), *Kuktepa* (Kushrabot district Kuvkalla village), *Kirgintepa*, *Koravultepa* (Kushrabot district Kizilbel village), *Koratepa*, *Avliyotepa*, *Boylartepa*, *Boytepa*, *Galvirtepa*, *Dungtepa*, *Ettitepa*, *Jalpoktepa* (Urgut district).

14. **Names of highlands:** (land places near mountain, mountain hills) *Bulakadir*, *Chukuradir*.

15. **Names of uplands:** the word upland (kir) means highland, hill on the land [10, p. 297]. For example: *Kaltakir* (Ishtikhan district), *Navkir* (Urgut district), *Tepakir* (Kushrabot district), *Turkmankir* (Nurabot district).

Besides several investigations on the toponymy and some researches, oronyms which are characterized as natural, ancient and stable in the system of toponymics were not collected in Uzbek onomastics and weren't studied in monographic aspect yet. As a result, scientific-theoretical issues of the oronymics branch in Uzbek onomastics, oronyms' place in toponymic system, linguistic nature, naming principles, lexical-semantic, dialectal, morphological features weren't studied yet.

As a part of toponymics, ononymics has its own object and subject to study. Oronymics is considered as one of branches which has theoretical and practical character.

The term *oronymics* consists of greek *oro*-mountain, *onyma*-name and *-ics*- about, and has the meaning “*about oroobjects*”.

The dimension of issues which is studied by oronymics is not clearly defined and showed in scientific sources of toponymics of the Uzbek linguistics. It is defined as following in scientific sources: “Oronymics is a branch of toponymics which study the complex of oronyms of definite language or region” [2, p. 82].

S.Koraev explains this term as: “Oronymics is a small branch of toponymics which study the origin of oronyms, laws of development and its functions” [14, p. 217]. E.Begmatov and N.Ulukov explain as “toponymics' branch which study the origin of oronyms and peculiarities” [1, p. 63].

Though these facts are considered as correct, we think that the branch of oronymics is much more wider in scientific-theoretical and practical sphere. Oronymics study the following issues which is connected with oronyms of onomastic layer of the language:

- 1) Linguistic and nonlinguistic factors of forming and developing of oronyms;
- 2) Historical, public traditions of naming oroobjects;
- 3) Linguistic features and its functions of oronymic indicators;
- 4) Naming principles of oroobjects;
- 5) Historical and modern forms of oronyms, and also linguistic changes in oronymic layer of the language;
- 6) Lexical-semantic peculiarities of oronyms;
- 7) Morphemic and forming features of oronyms;
- 8) Relations of appellative lexical layer and oronymic layer of the language;
- 9) Oronyms' relations with other types of toponyms: oykonyms, hydronyms, urbonyms, drimonyms, choronyms, agroonyms;
- 10) Data of forming oronyms in works on folklore, history, geography and ancient manuscripts;
- 11) Local dialects' features of oronymy;
- 12) Etymology of oronyms;
- 13) Issues of classification of oronyms;
- 14) Principles of forming oronymic maps, oronymic dictionaries.

The analysis of works on Uzbek oronymy indicates that besides linguistic analysis and notes, oronyms of the Uzbek language weren't studied special monographically.

Oronyms as special branch of toponymy is closely connected with national history, is linguistic layer and treasure which define particular sides of national language, people's social life, culture and spirituality. Oronyms as toponyms are rare examples of great cultural-spiritual heritage, national values.

Oronyms differentiate one type oroobjects by special naming and are characterized by transporting rich historical, social-political, natural-geographic information. The ancientness, stability, living, including different historical-geographic data of oronyms of the Uzbek language need to study the onomastic units by such subjects as history, geography, archeology, country study, linguistics. The most actual task of Uzbek toponymics is to study the achievements and experiences in oronym study, to create explanatory, etymological, orthographic, practical transcriptional, comparative dictionaries of Uzbek language's oronyms.

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